

WORK WITH PISA ASSIGNMENTS TO INCREASE THE LITERACY RATE OF STUDENTS

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ANNOTATION: The article describes the educational importance of using international assessment studies in the biological education system, the purpose of implementing biology PISA research tasks in secondary schools, and its role in the education system. Also, opinions on the development of students' knowledge of PISA tasks are presented. This is where studying the PISA program is important.

KEYWORDS: PISA, test, computer, standard, consortium, school, assessment, demand, organization, main results, level, questionnaire.

Introduction. In accordance with the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, setting priorities for the systematic reform of general secondary and extracurricular education, raising the moral, moral and intellectual development of the young generation to a new level in terms of quality, in order to introduce innovative forms and methods of education into the educational process, to achieve the Republic of Uzbekistan's entry into the ranks of the first 30 advanced countries of the world in the ranking of the PISA international program by 2030, as well as the international assessment of the quality of education in the public education system on the basis of the organization of research, the tasks of creating a national system for evaluating the quality of education aimed at assessing the level of literacy of students in reading, mathematics and natural sciences have been determined.

Tasks in the field of thinking

1. In nature, predators are said to be animals that feed on other animals. Predators refer to the animals that feed as prey.

Indicate which of the points given below are correct or incorrect for predators or which prey is suitable for them. Circle the answers against each of the thoughts.

Question Thar Unknown

Animals with sharp teeth are predators A V

Predators will be much larger in relation to their prey A V

Large animals will not be prey A V

Certain animals can also be prey to predators A V

Assignment 1. The content of the assignment corresponds to biology. The degree of complexity is average:

Farkhad and Feruzbek were given seeds of a sunflower plant from one plant. They laid soil on two gultuvaks of the same size.

Each gultuvak was planted with one seed. Farkhad took care of the plant in one gultuvak in his house, Feruzbek also began to care for the plant in the second gultuvak in his house. After a certain period of time, the children compared the plants they cared for and noticed that the plants were very different in growth and development from one.

Farkhad and Feruzbek cultivated plants in different ways. The plant in the first gultuvak in the picture was taken care of by Feruzbek, while the plant in the second gultuvak was taken care of by Farkhad. What is the difference in their plants depends on. Give a single example.

Assignment 2. A task with a low level of complexity related to the content of biology: which of these animals lives in the desert?

Assignment 3. "Heredity and variability" (application of the type of activity). The picture gives two cats belonging to the Menks breed.

Cats of this breed will not have a tail or will be too short. Can the tail of kittens, whose parents belong to the Menx breed, be long?

Comment on your yes / no answer.

Assignment 4. Task Group “milk” read the information given below and answer the questions.

Milk is the first food of mammals when they come into the world, receiving milk in sifto. For the healthy development of children, the milk content they consume must be of the same composition as the milk of their mothers.

The table below shows the main substances that are present in cow, Wolf and breast milk repellents. The data presented in the table are given how much fat, protein and carbohydrates are found in 100 g of milk.

Substances	Cow's milk (g)	Wolf's milk (g)	Breast milk (g)
Oil	3,9	9,6	4,0
Protein	3,4	9,2	1,4
Carb	4,9	3,4	7,0

In some cases, various legends walk about children who grew up sucking a wolf that grew up among wolves. In one such narrative, there are also legends about a child who lived in the forests of Europe in ancient times. The information presented in the table is evidence to prove these myths to be correct.

Question 1: using the data in the table, provide some evidence that these myths are correct.

Question 2: show evidence that myths are not correct in case you use the data in the table. You can buy different types of fat and protein-preserving milk in different quantities. Soliha bought two types of milk called “Baby”, One of which was in a white Second Blue package. The records on the packages provide information on the fat and protein content in the milk.

“Baby” 100g (white package)		“Baby” 100 g (Blue package)	
Oil	Protein	Oil	Protein
3.9g	3.4g	0.0 g	3.4g

Question 3: if milk is stored in a room temperature (for example 200 C) it will clot after a certain time. In addition, milk forms dense granules in the form of lumps.

Soliha wants to know what dense granules consist of. He stored milk in a 100g white package and 100G Blue package in a 200 C room order. After four days, both milk clotted. Ivigan milk from both packages saw that almost the same amount of dense granules were formed in the composition

Using the information about the milk composition in the packages, which of the information given below is an important conclusion for the formation of dense granules in this experiment?

- A) dense granules consist only of fat.
- B) dense granules consist only of protein.
- C) dense granules consist of protein and fat.
- D) it is impossible to determine whether dense granules are formed from protein or fat.

4. Fat in milk can only be used as a source of energy for a person.

Other substances in milk are carbohydrates, mineral salts and water, which of these substances can be used by a person as a source of energy.

Express your answer through “True” or “False”.

Substances	True / False
Carbohydrates	True / False
Mineral salts	True / False
Water	True / False

Assignment 5. Assignment “Antibiotic” Going to the doctor.

“Assalomu-alaykum Dr. The reason I come to you is that I have been coughing strongly for four days, the cough is getting worse every day. I was drinking an antibiotic that you wrote against this cough 2 months ago, this time it's not being affected.”

“You came to me and did a very right thing. You have done something wrong trying to treat yourself yourself: you should never take an antibiotic without a doctor's prescription. I take your throat from the back of your saliva for analysis and send it to the laboratory. In this way we will find out what is the disease with, after which I can prescribe the necessary treatment measures to help you.”

Question 1. As can be seen from the above conversation, the patient took an antibiotic to be free from coughing.

Which of the following is directly affected by the antibiotic?

- A) to cough
- B) to pain
- C) to bacteria

D) to viruses

Patient saliva antibiotic

The antibiogram was prepared by adding microorganisms to the patient's saliva in a petri Cup. Five different antibiotics a,V,S, D and Ye were used. After three days have passed, mycoorganisms have appeared outside the vicinity of the antibiotics that destroy them.

Can the doctor draw a conclusion based on an antibiogram made from the patient's saliva? Base each of your conclusions with "True" or "false".

Are the following conclusions made based on the evidence from the antibiotic correct? True or false

Microorganisms taken from the patient's throat are not affected by an antibiotic of Hech True or false

Antibiotic A can affect microalgae found in the patient's throat True or false

Antibiotic S is useful for combating microorganisms from the patient's throat True or false

The analysis of pedagogical studies shows that at present, the application of international assessment programs to the educational system requires new approaches to the organization of Education. The use of international assessment programs innovative technologies in education, in addition to biology, which is taught in secondary schools, increases interest in other subjects, there is always a demand for the implementation of interdisciplinary linking. As a result of this, students' logical thinking, creativity, research activities, cognitive activity are activated, independent analysis of Information, Processes, various information and protection in their own opinion, and the promotion and generalization of New-new thoughts form abilities.

In the educational process, modern approaches are making requirements aimed at mastering results-based education. The use of experiments acquired as a result of the same saabbli International Studies is gaining momentum. The following should be considered when identifying the purpose and specific aspects of International Assessment Research, the difficulties that arise when completing tasks related to it, and teaching students to overcome these difficulties:

- it is necessary to pay attention to which areas of Science the difficulties in these assignments apply:

-these tasks are knowledge of additional information (use of various tasks, deviation from texts) and, in addition, "unnecessary" and "excess" information in the task:

-using the likes of "Know", "reflect" and "apply" to find a solution of information that challenges students:

- demanding to have taasavur even about multi-option answers when completing these unusual tasks:

- understand that it is a complex that involves several interrelated questions and a task that requires design:

-it is a variety of topics that contain a large amount of information and that require answers with formats of different shapes to be given in different options (selecting an answer, writing words or Numbers, writing short or extended answers), with certain tasks being of the design type to complete them at a certain limited time:

- to connect these tasks with the processes of their own life during the execution period, to be able to apply their knowledge and skills in the unusual situations that occur in life:

- it requires the formation of task answers in the style of a table, diagram, graph:

-these assignments require the implementation of interdisciplinary connections.

Cited international assessment assignments and methodological guidelines for its implementation will be useful in preparing students for participation in international assessment programs PISA, TIMSS.

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